

Mapping Assessment Tools for Nature-Positive Decision-Making

Hummam M. Shaheen¹, Francisco S. Pinto², Mark van Nieuwstadt³, and John Garvey⁴

¹RCM2+, Lusófona University, Campo Grande 376, 1749-024 Lisboa, Portugal. Email: hummam.shaheen@ulusofona.pt

²RCM2+, Lusófona University, Campo Grande 376, 1749-024 Lisboa, Portugal. Email: francisco.pinto@ulusofona.pt

³Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, The Netherlands. Email: mark.vannieuwstadt@naturalis.nl

⁴Kemmy Business School, University of Limerick, V94 T9PX Limerick, Ireland. Email: John.Garvey@ul.ie

Abstract

Efforts to support nature-positive decision-making rely on a growing number of assessment tools for Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and Ecosystem Services (ES), yet the available tool landscape remains fragmented and difficult to navigate. Tools differ widely in scope and purpose, and there is limited evidence on how they are recognised and used in practice. This study addresses this gap by presenting a structured mapping of NbS and ES assessment tools and analysing their uptake among practitioners. In doing so, it enables a clearer alignment between tool selection and sectoral context. An initial search identified 275 items from publications, online databases and partner contributions, which were screened to 148 tools using a clear definition of an assessment tool. A survey of 737 respondents assessed awareness, knowledge and usage. The results show that only a small group of tools, including IUCN, InVEST and FAOSTAT, is widely recognised, while many others remain less visible. Engagement varies across regions, professional roles and work sectors, revealing uneven visibility and use. To improve access to information and better support tool selection for nature-positive decision-making, we provide insights into who uses which tools, how frequently they are used, and within which sectors.

KEYWORDS: Nature-based Solutions, Ecosystem Services, Assessment Tools, Tool Mapping, Tool Awareness, Tool Knowledge and Usage.

1. Introduction

The growing degradation of biodiversity and ecosystems has intensified the demand for strategic interventions. Nature-based Solutions (NbS) have emerged as opportunities to improve ecosystem functions able to support Ecosystem Services (ES), e.g., concrete social and economic benefits alongside ecological health. Alongside this, many tools have been developed to assess, monitor, and evaluate NbS and ES interventions.

However, these tools differ in scope, format, and purpose. Stakeholders, such as policymakers and environmental scientists, struggle to determine which tools align with their objectives. These difficulties are amplified by variations in how the term “tool” is conceptualised and applied across studies, which leads to inconsistencies in what is included, compared or evaluated. This situation shows the need to collect evidence from practitioners to understand how these tools are perceived and used in practice (who uses what, for which purpose, and when), which makes a dedicated survey necessary to map the current tool landscape.

This study addresses these challenges by presenting a structured mapping of NbS and ES assessment tools. Through a survey, the study assesses the tools' visibility (awareness), stakeholders' understanding of them (knowledge), and the extent of their application (usage), considering the respondents' background. It provides guidance into the development of new/existing tools (e.g., InVEST, ARIES, FAOSTAT) and their incorporation into structured decision-making processes (e.g. policy design, project monitoring and evaluation, and strategic planning). The research is conducted under the BIOFIN-EU project, which is an initiative dedicated to unlocking financial solutions for the protection and restoration of biodiversity.

2. Literature Insights

NbS are defined as actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore ecosystems to address societal challenges, while simultaneously providing benefits for biodiversity and human well-being and supporting ecosystem services (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2024). ES are often classified into four main categories (BIOFIN-EU, van Nieuwstadt, et al., 2024; Haines-Young & Potschin, 2012; Van der Ploeg et al., 2010): 1. Provisioning (tangible goods as food and water); 2. Regulating (benefits provided by ecosystem processes that moderate natural phenomena as flood control and pollination); 3. Cultural (non-material benefits as recreation and aesthetics); and 4. Supporting services (fundamental processes as soil formation and nutrient cycling). Although interest in NbS is increasing, its actual implementation across sectors is still relatively constrained, outlining the need for tools capable of assessing NbS performance, outcomes, and policy relevance to support planning and decision-making processes (Van Lierop et al., 2024).

Several studies have reviewed NbS and ES assessment tools, as shown in Table 1. They have catalogued and compared their intended functions, application domains, and methodological characteristics, but some remain narrow in scope. Common tools such as InVEST, ARIES, FAOSTAT, and SWAT appear frequently across reviews. Broader mapping efforts highlight the need to build practical, decision-oriented tool catalogues that are paired with consistent, reliable, and regular evaluation of available tools and to systematize tool information around clear practical use cases and user groups - who should use what, and under which conditions (Czúcz et al., 2018), while also indicating that a comprehensive catalogues alone is insufficient to address the complexity of the tool landscape, and that greater attention is needed to how tools are actually taken up in practice, including by whom and how often they are used.

Table 1. Reviews that perform a comparative analysis of NbS and ES tools, with number of tools mentioned

Review title	Citation	Nr.
Tools for Edible Cities: A Review of Tools for Planning and Assessing Edible Nature-Based Solutions	(Mino et al., 2021)	70
Nature-based solutions tools for planning urban climate adaptation: State of the art	(Voskamp et al., 2021)	44
Assessment of Biodiversity Measurement Approaches for Businesses and Financial Institutions	(De Ryck et al., 2024)	37
Tools for measuring, modelling, and valuing ecosystem services	(Neugarten et al., 2018)	30
A comparative assessment of decision-support tools for ecosystem services quantification and valuation	(Bagstad et al., 2013)	17
Study for a Methodological Framework and Assessment of Potential Financial Risks Associated with Biodiversity Loss and Ecosystem Degradation: Final Report	(EC et al., 2024)	15
A comparison of ecosystem services mapping tools for their potential to support planning and decision-making on a local scale	(Vorstius & Spray, 2015)	3

The use of digital and assessment tools to support biodiversity-related risk consideration and NbS decision-making is discussed mainly in relation to municipalities and other public actors, while evidence of systematic uptake by financial institutions remains limited (Biasin et al., 2024). Recent reviews of biodiversity footprinting approaches identify a growing portfolio of tools that are explicitly assessed for their relevance and applicability to financial institutions, including their ability to aggregate biodiversity impacts across portfolios and asset classes. However, these tools are largely characterised by methodological heterogeneity, limited standardisation, and uneven data coverage, which currently constrains their systematic operationalisation within conventional financial decision-making (Mokany et al., 2025; TNFD, 2023). Reviews emphasize the demand for integrated and user-oriented assessment frameworks to strengthen NbS implementation (Barker et al., 2024). Overall, the literature shows fragmented coverage and reinforces the value of consolidated mapping of existing NbS and ES tools to support effective, nature-positive decision-making.

3. Methodology

The tools were first identified through a systematic review that drew on peer-reviewed publications, technical reports, search engine queries, databases and projects (from, e.g., NatureServe, Oppla, and Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)), as well as contributions from BIOFIN-EU consortium members. This step produced a preliminary list of assessment tools, including the tool name, source, acronym, and website.

The list was subsequently filtered through a structured screening phase based on predefined criteria: conceptual alignment with the adopted definition of an assessment tool, operational status (whether the tool is active or has been discontinued), and the availability of accessible information. The definition of “tool” applied in this study distinguishes tools from non-tools by focusing on whether they offer interactive or

operational features that support decision-making, planning or environmental assessment. Only tools meeting this definition and the other screening criteria were retained.

Following the screening, a survey targeting experts and specialists in NbS and ES assessment was conducted to collect their feedback on the listed tools. The survey was designed to capture respondents’ awareness, knowledge and usage. A preliminary analysis of the survey data was carried out to describe respondents’ backgrounds and summarise how they interact with the tools. This was followed by a more detailed analysis exploring the links between tools, user experience and work sectors. The findings contribute to mapping the tools and set the foundation for future improvements to support decision-makers. Figure 1 presents the research methodology adopted to achieve the findings.

Figure 1. The research methodology

4. Empirical Analysis

4.1. Initial List

The review process allowed to identify a total of 275 potential tools. However, previous reviews have revealed nuanced differences in the interpretation of what constitutes an “assessment tool” (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Some studies have proposed pragmatic or context-specific operational definitions to delimit their scope (e.g. De Ryck et al. (2024)), this study similarly adopts an explicit working definition to guide the screening process. The definition adopted for this work is as follows:

“An assessment tool for nature-positive decision-making is considered any software, application, model, or web-based platform that integrate environmental and/or biodiversity considerations into decision-making processes and are designed to process data inputs to generate outputs such as reports, models, or metrics that

help users understand the impacts of their decisions on nature. They may support various functions, including risk assessment, impact evaluation, and scenario planning, and are used in fields such as project design, policy formulation, and investment analysis. Such tools incorporate interactive features and can be developed using programming languages or standard software applications. Methodologies provided solely in static formats like PDFs or web documents are not classified as assessment tools.”(BIOFIN-EU, Carlsson, et al., 2024). (adapted after)

According to this definition of “assessment tool”, a screening process was conducted leading to 148 tools (Appendix A). Figure 2 shows the percentage of each item according to their tool typology.

Figure 2. Percentage of each item according to their tool typology

4.2. Survey on Assessment Tools for Nature-Positive Decision-Making

A survey was developed using KoBo (<https://www.kobotoolbox.org/>) and refined through internal reviews before distribution to an international audience. It targeted professionals involved in environmental analysis and biodiversity decision-support, such as academics, technical experts, tool developers, consultants, and members of civil society. The questionnaire was structured to gather: (i) contextual information, (ii) respondents’ professional characteristics, and (iii) their level of familiarity with the listed tools, assessed through dedicated awareness, knowledge, and usage scales based on a six-point one-directional descriptor. Participants were reached through multiple channels, combining targeted invitations, professional networks, web-based sources, and citation-index platforms, using both purposive and snowball sampling approaches. A total of 737 individuals from 89 countries completed the survey. Most participants were affiliated with academic and research entities (88%). Geographically, responses were dominated by European participants (56%), followed by comparable proportions from Asia, Africa, and North America (around 10% each). Figure 3 illustrates the percentage of respondents from the academic/non-academic organizational roles according to their work sectors.

Figure 3. Percentage of Academia/non-Academia respondents according to their work sectors

4.3. Relevant tools’ Level of Knowledge and Usage

The respondents identified the tools that they are “aware of”, from a predefined tools master list. Among the 148 tools, only a few reached significant awareness thresholds: as IUCN Tool - 29%, InVEST - 26%, and FAOSTAT - 25%. Other tools, such as SWAT, ARIES, and i-Tree, showed awareness rates under 18%.

The level of knowledge and usage of each tool was defined by the respondents using a 6-point one-directional scale for each tool they are “aware of”. Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the percentages of respondents at each knowledge and usage level, for each tool. Those percentages represent the proportion of respondents who selected a given response category (e.g., “Limited”) out of the total number of respondents. Only tools recognized by at least 5 percent of respondents (i.e., n= 36 or more) were included in Figure 4 and Figure 5, to ensure representation of tools with sufficient visibility in the sample.

Figure 4. Percentage of respondents according to their level of knowledge regarding each tool

Figure 5. Percentage of respondents according to their level of usage regarding each tool

4.4. Analysis of respondents' background and knowledge of relevant tools

This section examines how respondents' organizational role shape their knowledge of the listed tools. Respondents indicated their level of knowledge for each tool they recognized, and these responses were examined in relation to their organizational role. To illustrate these patterns, a three-field Sankey diagram was developed to capture the flows between respondent characteristics, knowledge levels, and the tools. In Figure 6, the knowledge level functions as the central axis, with colour gradients used to distinguish the knowledge categories. Only tools that more than 50 respondents reported being "aware of" were included in the diagram, to maintain visual clarity and ensure readability.

Figure 6. Sankey diagrams show the relation of the respondent's organizational role and their tools' knowledge

For the sampled tools, clear differences emerge across organizational roles in terms of reported knowledge levels. Within each organizational role, academic and research-oriented respondents a pattern towards a stronger association with higher knowledge levels. Among professors, PhD holders, postdoctoral researchers, and senior researchers, approximately 18–21% report moderate knowledge, while extensive knowledge is reported by up to 5% within these groups. In contrast, among the non-academic respondents, within the management group, a pattern towards considerable knowledge is the most frequently reported level (22%). Within technical roles, the pattern relies on lower knowledge levels being more prevalent, as technician staff show higher shares of basic/limited knowledge.

Across the sampled tools that respondents are “aware of”, differences in knowledge depth become more explicit. Tools such as FAOSTAT, InVEST, and i-Tree show the highest shares of moderate to extensive knowledge among respondents aware of them. FAOSTAT stands out, with 56% of aware respondents reporting moderate, considerable, or extensive knowledge, followed by InVEST (40%) and i-Tree (44%). In contrast, tools such as NBSET, NBSEP, CAT, ARIES, and Adapt2Clima are more strongly associated with basic or limited knowledge among those aware of them. For these tools, limited knowledge alone accounts for between 34% and 40% of responses, while extensive knowledge remains marginal at 0-2%. Overall, this distribution indicates that while several tools have achieved broad awareness, depth of knowledge varies substantially across tools, with a small group showing stronger engagement and many others remaining known primarily at a basic or introductory level.

4.5. Analysis of respondents' background and usage of relevant tools

The respondents' role in their organization also shapes their usage of the tools. They reported how frequently they use the tools they are aware of, and these responses were analysed in connection with their organizational role. The resulting visualisations illustrate two main patterns: the variation in usage levels across respondent backgrounds, and the links between usage levels and specific tools. In Figure 7, the usage scale is the central dimension, with colour gradients used to distinguish levels of use. Also, to maintain visual clarity and readability, only the tools that more than 50 respondents reported being “aware of” were included.

Figure 7. Sankey diagrams show the relation of the respondent's organization role and their tools' usage

For the sampled tools, different usage patterns were identified across organizational roles, although overall usage intensity remains limited. Academic and research-oriented respondents report comparatively higher engagement, mainly at moderate or occasional levels, while frequent or extensive use remains marginal across academic groups (generally below 8%). For non-academic roles, the management staff who show a mixed usage profile, with 22% reporting occasional use and 19% reporting frequent use. In contrast, technician staff report rarely using tools in 30% of responses. Across all roles, a substantial share of respondents reports never using the tools, indicating limited regular use despite existing awareness.

Across the sampled tools that respondents are “aware of”, similar patterns are observed. Frequent or extensive use remains limited for most tools, while occasional, rare, or no use is more common. FAOSTAT stands out as the most actively used tool, with 36% of aware respondents reporting moderate to extensive use, followed by GFWCM, where 44% report occasional to moderate use. In contrast, tools such as ARIES, IBAT, Adapt2Clima, CAT, NBSEP, and NBSET are mainly associated with low usage intensity. Overall, the findings show that sustained and frequent use is concentrated in a small subset of tools.

4.6. Mapping Tools and Work sector Links

When we compare the tools with the respondents’ work sectors, clear patterns start to appear. Figure 8 shows which tools are linked to each sector based on what academic/non-academic respondents reported. Since people could choose more than one work sector and list several tools, the results capture a wide range of combinations.

Figure 8. The tools assigned to each work sector based on what academic/non-academic respondents reported

Some tools may show only a weak link to specific sectors in the results, even when they are documented as being used in those sectors. This suggests that sector-tool patterns may be only partly reflected within our survey sample. If participation from financial institutions or finance-focused practitioners was limited, tools mainly used in finance settings may appear less visible. For example, ENCORE does not stand out under “Financing” in our survey, although the ECB network uses ENCORE to assess ecosystem service dependencies and to aggregate these results at the portfolio level (Boldrini et al., 2023). At the same time, this may reflect current practice, where some tools are used mostly by specialised analysts or supervisory and research teams rather than in routine processes across the wider finance sector.

5. Discussion

The decline in global biodiversity has spurred the development of increasingly sophisticated tools for monitoring species populations, assessing ecosystem health, and quantifying ES. Despite these advances, the capacity of many stakeholders to apply such tools effectively in support of nature-positive decisions remains limited, particularly in lending and capital allocation. As the need for stronger, evidence-based support in biodiversity and ecosystem decision-making grows, the results of this study offer insights into how NbS and ES assessment tools are recognised and used by researchers, practitioners, and other stakeholders. By examining awareness, knowledge and usage, the study moves beyond simple tool cataloguing and provides a clearer understanding of how these tools operate within real professional contexts. This responds directly to the challenge raised in the introduction, by mapping how different stakeholder groups currently engage with existing tools, and by identifying patterns and gaps in awareness, knowledge, and usage from a user perspective.

For practitioners, planners, policymakers, and financial actors, the findings mainly reflect which tools are most visible within the respondent community, which is weighted toward academic users, and therefore offer an indication of where uptake is stronger in academic settings and where it may still need to translate into routine real-world application. This highlights the importance of clearer pathways for capacity building and adoption support to facilitate the transition of tool use from research contexts into practice. The analysis reveals a substantial gap between the large number of NbS and ES assessment tools currently available and their limited uptake in practice (academia vs non academia). This gap highlights that availability alone is insufficient and underscores the need for targeted efforts to improve communication, training and accessibility, so that tools are not only visible but effectively usable and understood by intended users. The patterns observed in awareness and usage also reveal dissemination trends for each tool and highlight areas where additional support may be needed to strengthen uptake and explore potential links in tool usage.

A notable contribution of this study is the mapping of links between tools and the work sectors of respondents, though not necessarily so representative of all sectors, e.g., business vs nature/NbS managers (Figure 3). These sector-tool connections help users see which tools could be useful in their field, where tool use is concentrated and where gaps remain. Understanding these relationships is valuable for both users and developers: users can better identify tools relevant to their sector, while developers gain insight into where tools may need adaptation or improved outreach.

Overall, the study enhances understanding of how NbS and ES assessment tools are perceived, known and applied in practice. By mapping awareness, knowledge, and usage patterns, and by revealing the links between tools and work sectors, it provides an empirical basis for improving how tools are organised, compared, and selected. Thus, it directly addresses the lack of comprehensive tool overviews, evaluation methods, and user-

oriented selection procedures identified in the literature. The study moves beyond cataloguing tools by offering evidence on who uses which tools, and how often. It also contributes to the future development of tools that are more accessible and relevant, raising concerns on communication efforts and capacity building pathways.

6. Concluding Remarks

This study presents a structured mapping of assessment tools used for NbS and ES. From an initial list of 275 items, a screening process based on the tool definition applied in this research resulted in 148 tools. Our sample of respondents is predominantly academic (+80%), with overall limited participation from business and finance sector (4%) and a stronger representation from conservation and environmental sectors (44% in nature protection). A survey with 737 respondents provided information on awareness, knowledge and usage. The IUCN tool, InVEST and FAOSTAT recorded the highest recognition. The results show low uptake and limited consensus in how the tools are known and used, revealing a clear gap between the number of available tools and the extent to which they are applied in practice.

The study also examined how tool engagement differs across roles. The Sankey graphs show that academic roles appear more often in the higher knowledge and usage levels, while technical staff, and engineers are more present in the basic and limited categories. They also show that tools such as InVEST, IUCN, and FAOSTAT are consistently linked to higher familiarity, whereas tools like NBSET, NBSEP, CAT, and Adapt2Clima are mainly associated with lower levels.

Links between tools and work sectors highlight where tools are most used and where uptake remains limited. This indicates uneven use across sectors and helps show where tools are relevant in practice to specific sectors. Overall, the study clarifies what tools are available, how well they are known and how often they are used. By combining the Sankey patterns and sector-tool links, the analysis provides a clearer view of how tools relate to user backgrounds and work contexts. It offers a basis for improving access and supporting more effective decision-making in NbS and ES assessments.

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Appendix A - Full List of Collected Assessment Tools

#	Acronym	Name	URL
1	3DFATMIC	Three-Dimensional Subsurface Flow, Fate and Transport of Microbes and Chemicals	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/three-dimensional-subsurface-flow-fate-and-transport-microbes-and-chemicals-3dfatmic
2	3DFEMWATER/3DFEM DLEWASTE	Three-Dimensional Finite Element Model of Water Flow Through Saturated-Unsaturated Media and Three-Dimensional Lagrangian-Eulerian Finite Element Model of Waste Transport Through Saturated-Unsaturated Media Models	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/3dfemwater3dlewaste
3	Adapt2Clima tool	Adapt2Clima tool	https://tool.adapt2clima.eu/en/home
4	Agriculture and Land Use National Greenhouse Gas Inventory Software	Agriculture and Land Use National Greenhouse Gas Inventory Software	https://www.climatelinks.org/resources/agriculture-and-land-use-national-greenhouse-gas-inventory-alu-software
5	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use Carbon Calculator	Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use Carbon Calculator	https://www.climatelinks.org/resources/agriculture-forestry-and-other-land-use-afolu-carbon-calculator
6	AGWA	Automated Geospatial Watershed Assessment Tool	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/automated-geospatial-watershed-assessment-agwa-tool
7	AQUATOX	AQUATOX	https://www.epa.gov/ceam/aquatox
8	ARIES	ARTificial Intelligence for Environment & Sustainability	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/aries-artificial-intelligence-for-environment-and-sustainability/
9	Arizona Online Environmental Review Tool	Arizona Online Environmental Review Tool	https://ert.azgfd.gov/
10	ATTILA	Analytical Tools Interface for Landscape Assessments	https://www.epa.gov/eco-research/analytical-tools-interface-landscape-assessments-attila-landscape-metrics
11	AWA	AgriAdapt Webtool for Adaptation	https://awa.agriadapt.eu/en
12	BEST	Benefits Estimation Tool	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/best-benefits-estimation-tool/

#	Acronym	Name	URL
13	BASINS	Better Assessment Science Integrating point & Non-point Sources	http://water.epa.gov/scitech/datait/models/basins/index.cfm
14	BASS	Bioaccumulation in Aquatic Systems Simulator	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/bioaccumulation-and-aquatic-system-simulator-bass
15	BIA-GBS	Biodiversity Impact Analytics powered by the Global Biodiversity Score	https://www.carbon4finance.com/product/biodiversity-impacts
16	BIAT	Biodiversity Impact Assessment Tool	https://www.issgovernance.com/esg/biodiversity-impact-assessment-tool/
17	B-INTACT	The Biodiversity Integrated Assessment and Computation Tool	https://www.fao.org/policy-support/tools-and-publications/resources-details/en/c/1305482/
18	BIOCHLOR	BIOCHLOR, Natural Attenuation Decision Support System	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/biochlor-natural-attenuation-decision-support-system
19	BIOPLUME III	BIOPLUME III, Natural Attenuation Decision Support System	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/bioplume-iii
20	BIOSCREEN	BIOSCREEN, Natural Attenuation Decision Support System	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/bioscreen-natural-attenuation-decision-support-system
21	BIP	Biodiversity Indicators Partnership	https://bipdashboard.natureserve.org/SelectCountry.html
22	BMS	Biodiversity Monitoring System	https://bms.biodiversity-monitoring.info/de
23	BPT	Biodiversity Performance Tool	https://bpti.biodiversity-performance.org/
24	Breakpoint Chlorination Simulator for Drinking Water Systems	Breakpoint Chlorination Simulator for Drinking Water Systems	https://usepaord.shinyapps.io/Breakpoint-Curve/
25	CANARY	CANARY	http://cfpub.epa.gov/si/si_public_record_report.cfm?subject=Homeland%20Security%20Research&dirEntryId=253555
26	CCAFS Mitigation Options Tool	CCAFS Mitigation Options Tool	https://ccafs.cgiar.org/contact-us
27	CHEMFLO™-2000	Software for Simulating Water and Chemical Movement in Unsaturated Soils	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/chemflo-2000-interactive-software-simulating-water-and-chemical-movement-unsaturated
28	Chloramine Formation and Decay Simulator for Drinking Water Systems	Chloramine Formation and Decay Simulator for Drinking Water Systems	https://usepaord.shinyapps.io/Unified-Combo/
29	Climate Action Tracker	Climate Action Tracker	https://climateactiontracker.org/
30	CMAQ	Community Multiscale Air Quality Model	https://www.epa.gov/cmaq
31	Co\$ting Nature	Co\$ting Nature	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/costing-nature/

#	Acronym	Name	URL
32	Condatis	Condatis	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/condatis/
33	CyAN app and CyANWeb	Cyanobacteria Assessment Network Mobile Application	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/cyanobacteria-assessment-network-application-cyan-app
34	CZAEM	Capture Zone Analytic Element Model	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/capture-zone-analytic-element-model-czaem
35	DATAR	The Diversity Assessment Tool for Agrobiodiversity and Resilience	https://www.agrobiodiversitypar.org/datar
36	EBM	Ecosystem-Based Management Tools Network	https://www.natureserve.org/conservation-tools/ecosystem-based-management-tools-network
37	EcoDIVER	Ecological Database and Interactive Visualizations of Evidence Records	https://www.epa.gov/ecodiver/about-ecodiver
38	EcoservR	Ecoserv-GIS in the R language	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/all/
39	EDM	Estuary Data Mapper	https://www.epa.gov/hesc/estuary-data-mapper-edm
40	EFDC	Environmental Fluid Dynamics Code	https://www.epa.gov/exposure-assessment-models/efdc
41	EIB Green Eligibility Checker	EIB Green Eligibility Checker	https://greenchecker.eib.org/
42	EIF InvestEU Sustainability Guarantee	EIF InvestEU Sustainability Guarantee	https://sustainabilityguarantee.eif.org/
43	ENCORE	Exploring Natural Capital Opportunities, Risks and Exposure	https://encorenature.org/en
44	EORA	EORA	https://www.worldmrio.com/
45	EPA H2O	EPA H2O	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/ecosystem-services-scenario-assessment-using-epa-h2o
46	EPANET	EPANET (all versions)	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/epanet
47	ESII	Ecosystem Services Identification & Inventory Tool	https://www.esiitool.com/
48	ESVD	Ecosystem Services Valuation Database	https://www.esvd.net/
49	ETDOT	Environmental Technologies Design Option Tool	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/environmental-technologies-design-option-tool-etdot
50	Evidence Map	Evidence Map	https://evidencemap.com/
51	EXAMS	Exposure Analysis Modeling System	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/exams-version-index
52	Ex-Ante Carbon-Balance Tool	Ex-Ante Carbon-Balance Tool	http://www.fao.org/3/ca7087en/CA7087EN.pdf
53	Exiobase	Exiobase	https://www.exiobase.eu/

#	Acronym	Name	URL
54	FAOSTAT	FAOSTAT	https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home
55	FECS	Final Ecosystems Goods and Services Scoping Tool	https://www.epa.gov/eco-research/final-ecosystem-goods-and-services-fees-scoping-tool
56	FOOTPRINT	FOOTPRINT	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/footprint-screening-model-estimating-area-plume-produced-gasoline-containing-ethanol
57	Free Chlorine and Cyanuric Acid System Simulator	Free Chlorine and Cyanuric Acid System Simulator	https://usepaord.shinyapps.io/cyanuric/
58	GCSOLAR	GCSOLAR	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/gcsolar
59	GeoPlatform Stormwater BMP Performance Database	GeoPlatform Stormwater BMP Performance Database	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/geoplatform-stormwater-bmp-performance-database-0
60	GID	Global Impact Database	https://www.impactinstitute.com/global-impact-data/
61	GIFMod	Green Infrastructure Flexible Model	http://gifmod.com/
62	GI-Val	Green Infrastructure Valuation Toolkit	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/green-infrastructure-valuation-toolkit-gi-val/
63	Global Biodiversity score	Global Biodiversity score	https://www.cdc-biodiversite.fr/le-global-biodiversity-score/
64	Global Database on Sustainable Land Management	Global Database on Sustainable Land Management	https://wocat.net/en/global-slm-database/
65	Global Forest Watch Climate Map	Global Forest Watch Climate Map	https://www.globalforestwatch.org/
66	Global Livestock Environmental Assessment Model	Global Livestock Environmental Assessment Model	Cert.outdoornebraska.gov
67	GPD	Good Practice Database	https://ndcpartnership.org/knowledge-portal/good-practice-database?areas[5641]=5641&language[5534]=5534&grouping[590]=590
68	Green Guide for Fund Managers	Green Guide for Fund Managers	https://greenguide.eif.org/
69	HELP	Hydrologic Evaluation of Landfill Performance Model	https://www.epa.gov/land-research/hydrologic-evaluation-landfill-performance-help-model
70	HSCTM2D	Hydrodynamic, Sediment, and Contaminant Transport Model	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/hscm2d
71	HSSM	Hydrocarbon Spill Screening Model	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/hydrocarbon-spill-screening-model-hssm
72	HydroloGIS	HydroloGIS	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/hydrologis/

#	Acronym	Name	URL
73	IBAT	Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool	https://www.ibat-alliance.org/
74	ICLUS	Integrated Climate and Land-Use Scenarios	https://www.epa.gov/gcx/about-gcx-integrated-land-use
75	ICR MPN	ICR Most Probable Number Calculator	https://mostprobablenumbercalculator.epa.gov/mpnForm
76	InFOREST	InFOREST	https://forest-data.unece.org/
77	InVEST	Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs	https://naturalcapitalproject.stanford.edu/software/invest
78	i-Tree Eco	i-Tree Eco	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/i-tree-eco/
79	IUCN	The IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions self-assessment	https://nbs-sat.iucn.org/
80	KANA Earth	KANA Earth	https://www.kana.earth/
81	Kentucky Biological Assessment Tool	Kentucky Biological Assessment Tool	https://kygisportal.ky.gov/arcgis/apps/webappviewer/index.html?id=d57ad568a4e44cc4b7c505952f3e898f
82	LakeCat	Lake-Catchment Dataset	https://www.epa.gov/national-aquatic-resource-surveys/lakecat-dataset
83	MAGIC	Habitat Network Maps	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/habitat-network-maps-magic/
84	MINTEQA2	MINTEQA2	https://www.epa.gov/exposure-assessment-models/minteqa2
85	MOFAT	Multiphase Flow and Multicomponent Transport	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/mofat-two-dimensional-finite-element-program-multiphase-flow-and-multicomponent
86	MPLAB	Cloud tools ecosystem	https://www.microchip.com/en-us/tools-resources/develop/mplab-cloud-tools-ecosystem#
87	MPN Calculator	Most Probable Number Calculator	https://mostprobablenumbercalculator.epa.gov/mpnForm
88	MULTIMED	Multimedia Exposure Assessment Model	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/multimed
89	NAPL	Nonaqueous Phase Liquid Simulator	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/non-aqueous-phase-liquid-napl-simulator
90	Natural Climate Solutions World Atlas	Natural Climate Solutions World Atlas	https://www.naturebase.org/
91	Nature-based Solutions Evidence Platform	Nature-based Solutions Evidence Platform	https://www.naturebasedsolutions-evidence.info/
92	Nature-based Solutions Evidence Tool	Nature-based Solutions Evidence Tool	https://www.naturebasedsolutions-evidence.info/evidence-tool/

#	Acronym	Name	URL
93	NDC-SDG Connections Database	NDC-SDG Connections Database	https://klimalog.idos-research.de/ndc-sdg/country/average
94	Nebraska Conservation and Environmental Review Tool	Nebraska Conservation and Environmental Review Tool	https://cert.outdoornebraska.gov/
95	NEVO	Natural Environment Valuation Online Tool	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/natural-environment-valuation-online-nevo-tool-2/
96	New Mexico Environmental Review Tool	New Mexico Environmental Review Tool	https://nmert.org/content/
97	North Carolina Natural Heritage Data Explorer	North Carolina Natural Heritage Data Explorer	https://ncnhde.natureserve.org/
98	OPAL	Offset Portfolio Analyzer and Locator	http://www.biodiversityoffsets.net/opal-new-free-open-source-stand-alone-soft%2%ADware-tool-cal%2%ADcu%2%ADlate-envi%2%ADron%2%ADmen%2%ADtal-losses-gains/
99	ORVal	Outdoor Recreation Valuation tool	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/orval-outdoor-recreation-valuation-tool/
100	OWL	Optimal Well Locator	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/optimal-well-locator-owl
101	PANORAMA	PANORAMA: Solutions for a Healthy Planet	https://panorama.solutions/en/explore-solutions?f%5B0%5D=ecosystem%3A63&f%5B1%5D=region%3A162&f%5B2%5D=theme%3A106
102	PESTAN	PESTAN (Pesticide Analytical)	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/pesticide-analytical-pestan-model
103	PRZM3	PRZM3	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/przm3-version-3123
104	RBI Checklist	Rapid Benefit Indicators Approach-Checklist Tool	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/rapid-benefit-indicators-rbi-approach
105	RBI Spatial	Rapid Benefit Indicators Approach-Spatial Analysis Toolset	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/rapid-benefit-indicators-rbi-approach
106	RECONNECT Measures Selector Tools	RECONNECT Measures Selector Tools	https://www.webscada.nl/reconnect/measures-and-tools/#/measures
107	REMChlor	Remediation Evaluation Model for Chlorinated Solvents	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/remediation-evaluation-model-chlorinated-solvents-remchlor
108	REMFuel	Remediation Evaluation Model for Fuel Hydrocarbons	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/remediation-evaluation-model-fuel-hydrocarbons-remfuel

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109	RePRisk	RePRisk	RepRisk World's largest ESG technology company
110	Resilience Atlas	Resilience Atlas	https://www.resilienceatlas.org/map?tab=layers&test=&layers=%5B%5D
111	SCAN-tool	SDG Climate Action Nexus tool	https://ambitiontoaction.net/scan_tool/
112	SENCE	Spatial Evidence for Natural Capital Evaluation	https://envsys.co.uk/sence/#how
113	SERAFM	Spreadsheet-based Ecological Risk Assessment for the Fate of Mercury	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/serafm-conceptual-model
114	SHEDS	Stochastic Human Exposure and Dose Simulation Models	https://www.epa.gov/chemical-research/stochastic-human-exposure-and-dose-simulation-sheds
115	SoIVES	Social Values for Ecosystem Services	https://www.usgs.gov/centers/geosciences-and-environmental-change-science-center/science/social-values-ecosystem
116	Stable Isotope Mixing Models for Estimating Source Proportions	Stable Isotope Mixing Models for Estimating Source Proportions	https://www.epa.gov/eco-research/stable-isotope-mixing-models-estimating-source-proportions
117	SUSTAIN	System for Urban Stormwater Treatment and Analysis Integration	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/system-urban-stormwater-treatment-and-analysis-integration-sustain
118	SWAT	soil and water assessment tool	https://swat.tamu.edu/
119	SWC	National Stormwater Calculator	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/national-stormwater-calculator
120	SWMM	Storm Water Management Model	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/storm-water-management-model-swmm
121	TEVASPOT	Threat Ensemble Vulnerability Assessment – Sensor Placement Optimization Tool Graphical User Interface	http://cfpub.epa.gov/si/si_public_record_report.cfm?subject=Hommel&%20Security%20Research&dirEntryId=257684
122	The Biodiversity Risk Filter	The Biodiversity Risk Filter	https://riskfilter.org/biodiversity/home/
123	The Environmental Benefits of Nature Tool	The Environmental Benefits of Nature Tool	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/the-environmental-benefits-of-nature-tool/
124	The NBS Benefits Explorer	The NBS Benefits Explorer	https://nbsbenefitsexplorerer.net/tool
125	The Place Standard tool	The Place Standard tool	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/the-place-standard-tool/
126	The Statutory Biodiversity Metric	The Statutory Biodiversity Metric	https://ecosystemsknowledge.net/resources/tool-assessor/the-statutory-biodiversity-metric/
127	The Water Risk Filter	The Water Risk Filter	https://riskfilter.org/water/explorer/

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128	ThinkHazard	ThinkHazard	https://thinkhazard.org/en/
129	ToxCast	Toxicity Forecaster	https://www.epa.gov/comptox-tools/toxicity-forecasting-toxcast
130	Traits	Freshwater Biological Traits Database	https://www.epa.gov/risk/freshwater-biological-traits-database-traits
131	Trase Earth tool	Trase Earth tool	https://trase.earth/
132	United Nations Biodiversity Lab	United Nations Biodiversity Lab	https://unbiodiversitylab.org/en/#more
133	VB	Virtual Beach	https://www.epa.gov/exposure-assessment-models/virtual-beach-vb
134	VIC	Variable Infiltration Capacity Model	https://www.appolutelydigital.com/ModelPrimer/chapter5_section9.html
135	Virginia Natural Heritage Data Explorer	Virginia Natural Heritage Data Explorer	https://vanhde.org/
136	Virulo	Virulo	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/virus-fate-and-transport-virulo-model
137	VLEACH	Vadose Zone Leaching Model	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/vadose-zone-leaching-vleach
138	VP	Visual Plumes	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/visual-plumes
139	VTT	Value Transfer Tool	https://www.esvd.info/value-transfer
140	WASP	Water Quality Analysis Simulation Program	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/water-quality-analysis-simulation-program-wasp
141	WATER REUSE CALCULATOR	Water Reuse Calculator	https://www.eartheconomics.org/waterreuse-calculator
142	WATERiD	Water Infrastructure Database	http://waterid.org/
143	WATERSHEDSS	Water, Soil, and Hydro-Environmental Decision Support System	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/watershedss
144	WhAEM2000	WhAEM2000	https://www.epa.gov/exposure-assessment-models/whaem2000
145	WHATIF	Watershed Health Assessment Tools Investigating Fisheries	https://www.epa.gov/exposure-assessment-models/whatif-watershed-health-assessment-tools-investigating-fisheries-download
146	WHPA	Wellhead Protection Area Model	https://www.epa.gov/water-research/wellhead-protection-area-whpa-model
147	WMOST	Watershed Management Optimization Support Tool	https://www.epa.gov/hydrowq/wmost
148	WW	WaterWorld v.2	www.policysupport.org/waterworld